

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

**Deliverable D7.9: Training & user onboarding activities report
(final)**

31/10/2022

 Training & user onboarding activities report (final)

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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

The objective of deliverable D7.9 is to report on the training and user onboarding activities carried out in NEANIAS. In this document we report the internal training activities aimed at project members, focusing on the introduction of open science practices, EOSC way of working, and capacity building sessions on core and delivery services. Then, we present the onboarding and training strategy for external users, covering the activities delivered by the thematic work packages, such as specific webinars and participation in international events, as well as the actions related to the NEANIAS Open Innovation events and the final NEANIAS Open Event.

1. Introduction

One of the most critical aspects in NEANIAS is the **delivery of training and capacity building activities for researchers, engineers and innovators**, both internal and external to the project. In particular, the NEANIAS roadmap foresees the organization and management of specific sessions and related materials on the following topics:

- *Open Science and EOSC / EOSC hub coaching*, for researchers primarily aboard the project as well as outsiders, especially under the perspective of EOSC hub and NEANIAS service portfolio.
- *Open Access coaching*, for project participants.
- *EOSC coaching*, for developers internal to the project or external coming from Open Innovation Calls and synergies established.
- *Training and coaching on NEANIAS services exploitation*, for end-users (researchers, industry and innovators), including core and thematic services.

The technical materials required for such sessions are assembled from **the inputs provided by the relevant work packages**, being tailored to the particular scope of each session. Capacity building in the project employs multiple means and tools, such as webcasts, webinars, online training platforms, social media, workshops and meetings.

Training, user onboarding and capacity building activities are crucial for the long-term sustainability of the project, largely contributing to visibility, dissemination, facilitating the engagement of end user communities, and gathering insightful feedback for the Technical and Strategy boards.

1.1.Changes from previous release report

The initial content and main structure of this document has been given by D7.6 [1] reporting the interim status and future plans for user onboarding, training and capacity building activities in NEANIAS during its first half duration. All the chapters have been updated according to the new events and activities organized to onboard and train users on the latest releases of the services and the novel services released.

1.2.Structure of the document

The document is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the internal training and capacity building activities; Section 3 covers the carried out and planned activities for onboarding and training external users; and Section 4 presents the conclusions and future steps.

2. Internal Training Activities

In the course of the project, a number of training and capacity building activities targeted to internal users -users directly involved in the project or members of the partner institutions and companies- have been carried out. The goal of these activities is threefold: (1) to **introduce the Open Science paradigm**, with a particular emphasis on FAIR practices, and present the EOSC ecosystem and the role of NEANIAS within that ecosystem; (2) to support service providers and project developers by **facilitating the integration of core and thematic services**, through tutorials, technical sessions and example use cases; and (3) to evaluate the maturity of the services by involving **internal domain experts in validation sessions**. These activities, coordinated by the relevant Work Packages, have played a fundamental role in pushing the NEANIAS service portfolio to its current state of stability and maturity (most services reached TRL8). Please note that links provided in this section are accessible and available only to the NEANIAS Consortium.

2.1 Open Science and Open Access

The first set of activities comprised **five specialized webinars about Open Science practices** mainly targeted at researchers onboard the project as well as outsiders, especially under the perspective of EOSC hub and NEANIAS service offerings.

2.1.1 Introduction to RDM, ARGOS for DMPs

This webinar focused on Data Management Plans. It started with an **introduction to Research Data Management** and what a Data Management Plan is, and then went on to introduce ARGOS, the OpenAIRE Data Management Plan preparation service.

- Date: Feb 21st, 2020
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Ellie Papadopoulou (ATHENA, OperAIRE)
- Available training material and recording: [Data Management Plans](#)

2.1.2 Open access publications

This webinar **introduced Open Access for publications**, its advantages for researchers, and the “Green and Gold” routes to open access¹, as defined in the Budapest Open Access Initiative Declaration.

- Date: July 10th, 2020
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Ellie Papadopoulou (ATHENA, OperAIRE)

¹ <https://www.springernature.com/gp/open-research/about/green-or-gold-routes-to-oa>

- Available training material and recording: [Open Access](#)

2.1.3 Research Data Management

This webinar went into **details on Research Data Management, with regard to Policies, Lifecycles, and Plans**. It presented the necessity for Open Data in the H2020 context, the requirement for a Data Management Plan, and then went into details of Research Data Management, such as actors, requirements, lifecycles, processes, etc. It also presented the vision for the integration of NEANIAS outputs into OpenAIRE.

- Date: February 3rd, 2021
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Ellie Papadopoulou (ATHENA, OperAIRE)
- Available training material and recording: [RDM Training](#)

2.1.4 RDM – Services: supporting FAIR data and management

This webinar went into **advice and best practices on how to apply FAIR for the NEANIAS services**, including a summary of requirements, a checklist to follow for repositories, and practical advice.

- Date: February 10th, 2021
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenters: Ellie Papadopoulou (ATHENA, OperAIRE), Iryna Kutchma (OpenAIRE)
- Available training material and recording: [RDM Training - Applying FAIR](#)

2.1.5 The Zenodo long-term digital preservation repository

This webinar focused on **the use of Zenodo as a long-term, catch-all, digital preservation repository for research outputs coming from the NEANIAS project**. Zenodo as a repository service was introduced first, then its REST API was presented as a means for service providers to upload their research data. Finally, new and upcoming functionality of Zenodo was presented, such as the ability to create custom metadata attributes based on well-established schemas.

- Date: March 18th, 2021
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenters: Alex Ioannidis (Zenodo)
- Available training material and recording: [Zenodo Training](#)

2.2 EOSC Training and Onboarding

The second set of activities dealt with **EOSC coaching and training**, so NEANIAS service providers become familiar with EOSC standards, procedures and practices. These activities involved a series of webinars, informative sessions and events that provided insights on the EOSC ecosystem.

2.2.1 Presentation of the NEANIAS service model

In this dedicated session, NEANIAS service providers were presented with the **standard EOSC service model**. The Provider and Resource profiles were introduced by means of practical examples, along with specific support to complete the relevant data sheets for a successful onboarding.

- Date: December 17th, 2020.
- Presenter: Christos Tsiakaliaris (ATHENA)
- Available training material: [EOSC service model](#) and [EOSC definitions](#)

2.2.2 EOSC onboarding and service management procedures

This special training session presented the **stages of the EOSC service onboarding process**. Afterwards, it went on to introduce the service management toolset, comprising the NEANIAS service catalogue², the NEANIAS ticketing system, and the NEANIAS wiki, plus additional service-specific tools. Then, the service management processes and incident handling procedures were explained in detail.

- Date: March 10th, 2021
- Presenter: Christos Tsiakaliaris (ATHENA)
- Available training material: [EOSC Onboarding](#) and [Service management](#)

2.2.3 Involvement into EOSC Secretariat

NEANIAS Project Manager Eleni Petra became member of the EOSC Training and Skills Working Group of the EOSC secretariat, with the goal of building competence and capabilities for EOSC, providing a sustainable training infrastructure to support EOSC and ensure its uptake. Similarly, NEANIAS Technical Manager Georgios Kakalettris became member and the Architecture Working Group, aiming at providing a technical framework suitable to enable and sustain an evolving EOSC federation of system, including standards, APIs and protocols. NEANIAS WP4 Leader Eva Sciacca became co-chair of the EOSC-A Task Force on Technical Interoperability of Data and Services, with the goal of supporting the development of the EOSC Core and Exchange interoperability guidelines.

2.2.4 Participation in EOSC-hub week 2020 seminars

Representatives from all NEANIAS Work Packages **attended the EOSC Hub Week 2020**³, a three-day event held between May 18th-20th with more than 800 participants. The event

² <https://catalogue.neanias.eu/>

³ <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/eosc-hub-week-2020-goes-virtual>

brought together partners, key players and stakeholders from the EOSC network, with the goal of **aligning efforts and exploiting synergies for a successful and sustainable materialization of the EOSC ecosystem**. In a series of plenary sessions, seminars and technical workshops, the strategic EOSC vision, along with useful insights and best practices concerning EOSC service onboarding and data management, were provided.

2.2.5 Participation in ESFRI-EOSC workshop 2020

NEANIAS participated in the 2nd edition of the workshop on the connection of ESFRI Research Infrastructures to EOSC, which took place on October 6th and 7th, 2020. This event brought together ESFRI and EOSC stakeholders to **showcase added-value concepts for users and providers, with concrete use cases, good practices and novel approaches to Open Science** and cross-domain data sharing within the EOSC framework. Besides, new tools for thematic providers were presented, concerning networking, computing and data services.

2.2.6 Participation in the EOSC Symposium

NEANIAS took part in the EOSC Symposium between October 19th and 22nd, an interdisciplinary event organised by the EOSC Executive & Governing Board with the support of the EOSC Secretariat. This milestone event, brought together researchers, data scientist, infrastructure providers, EOSC projects and representatives from the EU member countries in a unique opportunity to discuss the final steps toward **the implementation materialisation of a first version of a fully-fledged European Open Science Cloud**. In particular, the event covered the highlights of EOSC during the first two years after launch, focusing on lessons learnt and outlining the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda.

2.3 Training on NEANIAS Core services

Core services constitute **one of the pillars of the NEANIAS architecture**, providing a transversal, general-purpose, and reusable infrastructure that supports a number of functionalities (e.g., Authentication, Accounting...) to be exploited by higher-level thematic services. A series of capacity building technical sessions organised by the Core service providers are planned or have already been conducted, with the aim of **supporting Thematic Service providers in the integration process according to the NEANIAS development roadmap**. The sessions include architectural specifications, hands-on demonstrations and practical use cases.

2.3.1 AAI

This event **introduced the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) service**, introduced also the OpenID Connect protocol that it supports, and gave specific instructions to the service providers on how to successfully integrate with it.

- Date: September 17th, 2020
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Giorgos Papanikos (CITE)

- Training material and recording: [AAI Demo & Q&A Session](#)

2.3.2 Logging

This session **introduced the Logging service as deployed and configured for the NEANIAS project** and gave instructions to service providers on how to properly integrate with it. The user interface of the Logging service was also demonstrated.

1. Date: October 29th, 2020
2. Duration: 1 hour
3. Presenter: Giorgos Papanikos (CITE)
4. Training material and recording: [Logging Service Demo](#)

2.3.3 Accounting

This webinar **introduced the accounting service as implemented for the NEANIAS project**. Its relationship with the *Logging* service was presented, and instructions were given to service providers on how to properly integrate with it. The user interface of the accounting service was also demonstrated.

1. Date: January 29th, 2021
2. Duration: 1 hour
3. Presenter: Stratis Giannopoulos (CITE)
4. Training material and recording: [Accounting Logging Demo](#)

2.3.4 GARR Cloud training: OpenStack, Docker and Kubernetes

This 2-hour long session, in the form of a webinar, **introduced three aspects of the cloud offerings at GARR**. It started with an overview of **Openstack** and a demonstration of its front-end. It continued with an introduction of **Docker**, as a means to package and deploy applications. Finally, it concluded with an introduction and demonstration of **Kubernetes**, which is the most recent addition to the GARR cloud offerings. In the GARR deployment of Kubernetes, the latter uses Docker as the container engine and this is why Docker was also presented in this webinar.

- Date: September 29th, 2020
- Duration: 2 hours
- Presenters: Claudio Pisa, Alberto Colla, Alex Barchiesi, Matteo Di Fazio, Delia Passalacqua, Marco Lorini (GARR)
- Training material and recording: [Garr Cloud training webinar](#)

2.3.5 Applied Kubernetes webinar

This webinar focused in more detail in **the use of Kubernetes to deploy services at GARR**. It was deemed necessary as the Kubernetes technology was selected by many thematic service providers as the “new” way to deploy their services to make optimal use of the resources available to them at GARR, and due to the steep learning curve of the Kubernetes system. In this one and a half hours session, the basics of Kubernetes were reintroduced, an existing

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NEANIAS service (U3, *uw-map*) was showcased as it moved from Docker on a VM to a Kubernetes deployment, and the batch Jobs as supported by Kubernetes were surveyed.

- Date: April 14th, 2021
- Duration: 1.5 hours
- Presenters: Nikos Chondros, Michalis Konstantopoulos (NKUA)
- Training material and recording: [Applied Kubernetes](#)

2.3.6 Service monitoring / Internal (nagios)

This webinar presented the monitoring capabilities of the interak **NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure**, based on Nagios, InfluxDB, Prometheus and Grafana, and gave advice on how service providers can take full advantage of it to monitor their services from an “internal” point of view, including network availability and even operating system status regarding security upgrades.

- Date: November 21st, 2021
- Duration: 2 hours
- Presenter: Claudio Pisa (GARR)
- Training material and recording: [Internal Monitoring Training](#)

2.3.7 Monitoring / External (Argo)

This is a webinar that is currently in the planning stage. It will present **the Argo monitoring service**, which is already an EOSC service, and advice on how service providers can prepare “probes” that will allow Argo to monitor their service’s “health”, and how they can in turn get metrics on its availability. This will monitor the services from the “outside”, from the user’s point of view.

This webinar did not materialize as the meetings between the core WP7 team and Argo team were deemed sufficient for the proper use of Argo by NEANIAS.

2.3.8 Service Management System (SMS)

This webinar presented the Service Management System, which implements the needed workflows in support of the NEANIAS Service management Framework. The system was introduced, with a live demo of some of the workflows, to showcase its use as well as its usefulness.

- Date: October 21st, 2021
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Attila Farkas (SZTAKI)
- Training material and recording: [SMS Training](#)

2.3.9 Short trainings on plenary and technical board meetings

Besides the capacity building sessions, a number of **short complementary demonstrations** were conducted during the NEANIAS 3rd Plenary Meeting, held on November 19-20th, 2020, and during the 3rd Technical Board meeting on January 22th, 2021 (recordings available [here](#)). These demonstrations were mostly live sessions, not exceeding 10 minutes and focusing on **practical aspects related to core services implementation and use**. The contents of these live demos are summarized below:

2.3.10 Portal and Catalogue

This short session introduced a preliminary **working version of the NEANIAS service catalogue**, showcasing the site structure and the service browsing and filtering functionalities.

- Date: November 20th, 2020
- Presenter: George Papastefanatos (ATHENA)

2.3.11 Logging service

This live demonstration focused on the **integration with the NEANIAS logging service**, presenting a simulated service integration that highlighted the most relevant technical aspects to be considered to successfully push log entries to the aggregator, such as log formatting, Filebeat configuration (endpoints, certificates) and log browsing in Logstash.

- o Date: November 20th, 2020
- o Presenter: Georgios Papanikos (CITE)

2.3.12 C3.1 AI Gateway and ADAM API

This session **addressed core service C2, the Data Exploration Service**, in particular its three components: the Explorer, Jupyter Hub, and ADAM API. The live demonstration showcased an example on the Jupyter environment describing the four steps that constitute the typical workflow of ADAM API: user authentication, retrieval of datasets from registered endpoints, search for specific data products and access to the data.

- o Date: November 19th, 2020
- o Presenter: Simone Mantovani (MEE0)
- o Available demo material: [ADAM API](#)

2.3.13 C3.3 Horovod service (3rd Project meeting, 19 NOV 2020)

In this session, a short demo of the Horovod service was presented, **introducing a project-level, scalable solution for distributed training of deep learning models**, exploitable by all the thematic services. The demo focused on how to access the Horovod cluster through Jupyter Hub to execute model training tasks using the Tensorflow and Keras libraries. The system architecture and deployment specifications were explained.

- o Date: November 19th, 2020.

- Presenter: Attila Farkas (SZTAKI)
- Available demo material: [Distributed Deep Learning-Horovod](#)

2.3.14 Visual Discovery framework integration to Visualization Gateway

This live demonstration showed working examples on JupyterHub of **two fundamental pieces of the Visual Discovery framework**: VisIVO, the core visualization package; and Splotch, a high-performance particle visualizer. The two services are part of the Visualization Gateway, accessible by all thematic services.

- Date: November 19th, 2020.
- Presenter: Eva Sciacca (INAF)
- Available demo material: [VDFramework](#)

2.3.15 Spark demonstration

This demonstration showed a practical use case of the Spark core service for hyperparameter optimisation, applicable to machine learning tasks of the thematic services.

Date: January 22th, 2021

Presenter: T. Cecconello (UNIMIB)

2.4 Thematic Services Internal Validation

In the context of each main release of the NEANIAS thematic services, internal validation sessions on the thematic services were performed to **evaluate functionalities and maturity**. During these sessions, also external users were involved. The validation process involved a total end-user from the target communities, namely underwater, atmospheric and space. The validators, selected by the service providers, spanned a wide range of technical profiles, including students, academics, researchers and industry professionals. In total, 161 end-users validated the underwater services; 324 end-users validated the atmospheric services, and 171 end-users validated the space services. The validation results were **predominantly positive, allowing service providers to spot bugs and issues** affecting performance and stability, that were promptly resolved. Moreover, the validation process provided specific, valuable first-hand feedback on how to improve the thematic services according to the needs of the target communities, both from a functional and UX point of view.

Reports summarizing the validation results and feedback received for each service are available in the corresponding deliverables D2.9 [2] (underwater), D3.9 [3] (atmospheric) and D4.9 [4] (space).

3. External Onboarding and Training Activities

3.1 User board coordination

NEANIAS User Board set up a series of actions, involving work packages 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6, to **increase visibility of the project and coordinate the engagement and onboarding** of external users. These activities, presented in [the project's General Meeting](#) held in April 2021, included:

- Promoting the presentation of NEANIAS thematic services **in seminars and workshops**.
- Conducting novel **service validation rounds in May 2021 and in July 2022**, involving external users from the target communities, up to 200 per thematic service, to reach a total of at least, 1.800 users.
- Generating **multimedia material to increase the visibility of the developed services** within the target communities, such as video tutorials and demonstration videos with a scientific approach).

3.2 Thematic Services Onboarding and Training

Following the first release of NEANIAS thematic services, service providers and related Work Packages, in coordination with the NEANIAS User Board, have **planned a number of actions to increase the visibility of the NEANIAS service offerings** within the research ecosystem, engaging end-users from the target communities (underwater, atmospheric and space) and **drawing new potential users** from synergistic sectors and industries through the **joint development of new business opportunities**. These activities include the organisation of technical tutorials and webinars that connect users and service providers, the organization of multidisciplinary events such as Workshops and Hackathons, looking for potential applications that reach beyond the initial scope of the services, the participation in conferences and other scientific venues that highlight the potential of NEANIAS services, and the generation of detailed user documentation and support material that facilitates the onboarding process.

3.2.1 Underwater specific activities

NEANIAS underwater service providers onboarding activities comprise the co-hosting of the *Blue Research and Innovation Days* event and the organization of several practical sessions at universities focusing on the developed services.

3.2.1.1 Blue Week (Blue projects/ community)

During April 21st-23rd, NEANIAS co-hosted the *"Blue Research and Innovation Days"⁴* event, together with other European and National (Greek) projects. The primary goal was **to create**

⁴ <https://blueinnovation2021.athenarc.gr/>

a forum of discussion, with more than 500 attendees, bringing together key actors from the scientific community and industry, to identify **overlapping working areas, create synergies and shape future activities focusing on 'Blue economy'**, i.e., the "sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, and jobs while preserving the health of ocean ecosystem."⁵

Within the framework of this event, the developers of the underwater services (U1, U2, U3) provided a detailed presentation of their solutions by means of audiovisual material (presentations, live demonstrations), showcasing their capacities, current results and future perspectives, thus raising awareness and interest among the event participants.

NEANIAS also took part in the *Blue Hackathon*, a **2-day contest** aimed at data scientists, students, researchers and representatives from both private and public sectors, **focused on developing innovative solutions for blue-economy related challenges**. In particular, NEANIAS introduced two challenges based on services U1 and U3. The participants could access and use the tools to tackle problems like online image annotation of underwater images, and submarine cable route design.

3.2.1.2 Practical Lessons

- **U1 Practical Lesson**

Practical lesson with undergraduate students from the University of Athens and the University of Milan, showing how they **can process the swath data** using service U1. 10 students used the service and produced their own bathymetric maps.

- Date: April, 2021
- Presenters: D. Lampridou (NKUA)

- **U2 Practical Lesson**

Practical lesson with undergraduate students from the University of Girona, showing the **camera calibration task of service U2**. 60 students used the service and calibrated their own cameras.

- Date: March, 2021 (different practical sessions)
- Presenter: R.Garcia (CORONIS)

- **U3 Practical Lesson**

Practical lesson with undergraduate students from the National Technical University of Athens, showing the can perform **seabed classification** using the U3 service. 68 students used

⁵ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/infographic/2017/06/06/blue-economy>

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the service and produced seabed classification maps based on multi-spectral multi-beam echosounder data.

- Dates: December, 2021 and June, 2022 (different practical sessions)
- Presenter: K. Karantzos (ATHENA)

3.2.1.3 Workshops and Webinars

The NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services have been showcased in the following workshops and webinars:

- NEANIAS Underwater Services Webinar
Date: 20/04/2021
Location: Online
Presenters: Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA), Kalliopi Baika (Aix-Marseille Université), Eleni Petra (NKUA)
Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/394-neanias-underwater-services-webinar>
- Underwater services: calibration tests workshop
Date: 30/08/2021
Location: Aegina, Greece
Presenters: Kalliopi Baika (Aix-Marseille Université)
Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/626-calibration-tests-underwater-workshop>
- NEANIAS Underwater services CNRS Workshop
Date: 30/10/2021
Location: Aigina, Greece
Presenters: Kalliopi Baika (Aix-Marseille Université)
Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/630-neanias-underwater-services-organized-a-cnrs-workshop>
- NEANIAS workshop on 2nd release of services U2, U3
Date: 19/11/2021
Location: Aix-Marseille University

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Presenters: Kalliopi Baika (Aix-Marseille Université)

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/632-neanias-held-a-workshop-on-2nd-release-of-services-u2-u3>

- An Accessible Ocean Workshop

Date: 10/05/2022

Location: Online

Presenters: Konstantinos Karantzos (ATHENA), Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA), Danai Lampridou (NKUA), Josep Quintana Plana (CORONIS), Paul Wintersteller (TELEDYNE), Ricard Campos (CORONIS), Makis Ntouskos (NKUA), Kalliopi Baika (Aix-Marseille Université), Effie Zafeirakopoulou (NKUA)

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/673-neanias-ocean-decade-laboratories-an-accessible-ocean>

- NEANIAS Open Innovation workshop.

Date: 05/09/2022

Location: Athens & Online

Presenters: Paraskevi Nomikou, Makis Ntouskos (NKUA), Lampridou Danai (NKUA)

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/796-neanias-open-innovation-workshop>

- NEANIAS Underwater workshop at the 1st International Conference of Mediterranean Harbour and Coastal Archaeology 2022

Date: 29/09/2022

Location: Aix-Marseille University

Presenters: Konstantinos Karantzos (ATHENA), Josep Quintana (CORONIS), Paul Wintersteller (TELEDYNE)

Link: <https://aiginaharbourcity.com/neanias.html>

- NEANIAS workshop at Fisheries and Aquaculture department of University of Patras

Date: 19/10/2022

Location: Patras, Greece

Presenters: Josep Quintana (CORONIS), Ricard Campos (CORONIS), Makis Ntouskos (NKUA), Eleni Petra (NKUA)

- NEANIAS Innovation workshop

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Date: 26/10/2022

Location: Athens & Online

Presenters: Paraskevi Nomikou, Makis Ntouskos (NKUA), Josep Quitana (CORONIS)

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/848-innovation-and-assesment-workshop>

3.2.1.4 Production of training resources

WP2 service providers have produced documentation for all services locate online [here](#), which includes explaining the scientific approach and user guides.

Additionally, a webinar recording is available via NEANIAS YouTube channel here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ulVdCgrTNSU>. In the webinar, all underwater services are presented.

Training material were also prepared, for instance the examples on how to use this service is also provided in the service and was used in different events to facilitate user's engagement and to support NEANIAS Business cases.

3.2.1.4. Presentations and Conferences

The NEANIAS Underwater thematic services have been highlighted into the following conferences and events.

- NEANIAS Underwater presented at Map the Gaps Symposium
Date: 27-28/10/2022
Location: Southampton & Online
Presenters: Paul Wintersteller (TELEDYNE)
Link: <https://www.mapthegaps.org/symposium-2022>

- NEANIAS Open Event
Date: 22-23/09/2022
Location: Barcelona & Online
Presenters: Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA)
Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/neanias-open-event/29-main/734-open-event-agenda>

- NEANIAS Underwater participated at EGU
Date: 23-27/05/2022

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Location: Vienna & Online

Presenters: Konstantinos Karantzas (ATHENA/NTUA)

Link: <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU22/EGU22-11661.html>

- NEANIAS Underwater presented at GeoHub 2022.

Date: 15 -20/05/2022

Location: Venice & Online

Presenters: Paul Wintersteller (TELEDYNE)

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/708-neanias-underwater-presented-at-geohub-2022>

- NEANIAS project presented at the 35th Nordic Geological Winter Meeting 2022.

Date: 11-13/05/2022

Location: Reykjavik

Presenters: Poster Title "Identification of Marine Geohazards with the use of NEANIAS service"

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/710-neanias-project-presented-at-the-35th-nordic-geological-winter-meeting-2022>

- NEANIAS contributed in the Ocean Decade initiative of United Nations, by organizing a Satellite Event in the upcoming "An Accessible Ocean" Ocean Decade Laboratories event.

Date: 10/05/2022

Location: Budapest/Remote

Presenters: Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA), Konstantinos Karantzas (ATHENA/NTUA), Josep Quintana Plana (CORONIS), Paul Wintersteller (TELEDYNE)

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/news/31-upcomingevent/673-neanias-ocean-decade-laboratories-an-accessible-ocean>

- NEANIAS Underwater presented at the UNESCO headquarters.

Date: 10/12/2021

Location: Paris

Presenters: Jafar Ambar (Aix-Marseille Université)

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/636-neanias-underwater-presented-at-the-unesco-headquarters>

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- NEANIAS Underwater presented in Maritime Archaeology Graduate Symposium 2021
Date: 25-26/11/2021
Location: Aix-Marseille University
Presenters: Kalliopi Baika (Aix-Marseille Université), Jafar Anbar (Aix-Marseille Université)
Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/634-neanias-underwater-presented-in-maritime-archaeology-graduate-symposium>
- Presentation of NEANIAS and its EOSC services to the Municipality and Port Authorities of the island city of Aegina.
Date: 30/09/2021
Location: Aegina
Presenters: Kalliopi Baika (Aix-Marseille Université)
Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/628-presentation-of-neanias-and-its-eosc-services-to-the-municipality-and-port-authorities-of-the-island-city-of-aegina>
- NEANIAS underwater services presented at the 2nd International Conference Dive in Blue Growth on the Promotion of Accessible Underwater Cultural Heritage Sites.
Date: 13/05/2021
Location: Online
Presenters: Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA), Kalliopi Baika (Aix-Marseille Université), Paul Wintersteller (TELEDYNE), Konstantinos Karantzaos (ATHENA), Josep Quintana (CORONIS), Danai Lampridou (NKUA), Effie Zafeirakopoulou (NKUA), Jafar Anbar (Aix-Marseille Université)
Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/400-neanias-underwater-services-presented-at-the-2nd-international-conference-dive-in-blue-growth-on-the-promotion-of-accessible-underwater-cultural-heritage-sites>
- NEANIAS participated in the 20th webinar "Risk, Disaster and Crisis Management with the Use of Modern Technologies at National and International Level"
Date: 14/10/2021
Location: Online
Presenters: Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA)

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/549-neanias-participated-in-the-20th-webinar-risk-disaster-and-crisis-management-with-the-use-of-modern-technologies-at-national-and-international-level>

- NEANIAS at the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO)

Date: 12-14/02/2020

Location: Athens

Presenters: Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA), Konstantinos Karantzalos (ATHENA),

Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/53-neanias-attended-european-multidisciplinary-seafloor-and-water-column-observatory-emso>

3.2.1.5 Underwater Services User Feedback

During the onboarding activities as well as consequent usage of the Underwater services, following the processes defined in the Service Management System that governs the development, delivery, and operation of the NEANIAS services, the end users were invited to provide their feedback on various aspects of the services as perceived by their engagement with them. These responses were collected and aggregated to convey the qualitative and quantitative performance and perceived by the service consumers utilizing user feedback from system usage.

Out of the total number of Underwater Service users, a total of 80 users opted to provide feedback on the service usage. The level of domain expertise of these users is showing in the following Figure 1 - Underwater domain user expertise

Figure 1 - Underwater domain user expertise

The users were asked to provide their feedback in the following service aspects:

- User Interface Experience
- Evaluation of end results

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- Evaluation of service performance
- Willingness to recommend the service

The users were asked to grade their impressions on a scale of 1 to 3, indicating their satisfaction. From Poor to Satisfactory or Excellent.

With respect to the User Interface experience, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 2 - Underwater UI/UX across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 3 - Underwater UI/UX by user domain expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

Figure 2 - Underwater UI/UX across all users

Figure 3 - Underwater UI/UX by user domain expertise

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Evidently, 70% of the users find the User Interface interactions with the service satisfactory or excellent, but as we move into the responses per domain level expertise, the trend becomes more apparent that as the domain relevance) and hence the experience with existing tools and interfaces available in the domain, the users are more satisfied with the services user interface, understanding the complexity of the challenge increases (increasing from 12% to 28% and even 50% of excellent impressions as we progress from low to expert users.

Similarly, moving to the result evaluation, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 4 - Underwater Results across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 5 - Underwater Results by user domain expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

Figure 4 - Underwater Results across all users

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Figure 5 - Underwater Results by user domain expertise

Also in these figures, we can observe that as the domain expertise increase, so does the user satisfaction with the results obtained, from 70% up to 100% of the received feedback.

Service performance wise, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 6 - Underwater Performance across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 7 - Underwater Performance by user domain expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

Figure 6 - Underwater Performance across all users

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Figure 7 - Underwater Performance by user domain expertise

Users with lower expertise on the domain seem more troubled by the performance of the service, while as the relevance of the users with the domain increases, the feedback is more appreciative with the performance characteristics that NEANIAS Underwater services offer evolving from 67% (satisfactory and excellent) for low relevance users to 82% and 100% for high and expert users respectively.

Coming to the important factor of whether the users would be willing to recommend the service to their colleagues, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 6 - Underwater Performance across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 7 - Underwater Performance by user domain expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

Figure 8 - Underwater willingness to recommend across all users

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Figure 9 - Underwater willingness to recommend by user domain expertise

Here the impressions are very encouraging from the service users as almost all users would recommend the Underwater services they used.

3.2.2 Atmospheric specific activities

Atmospheric thematic services onboarding activities have so far been focused on promoting the services by means of the following actions:

- Organization of workshops to engage users and promote service reuse.
- Participation in webinars and events to promote the service developments and engage end-users to become aware and be a part of NEANIAS community
- Promotion of the project Open Call opportunities in WP5 activities
- Presentation and testing of the atmospheric services at the Environmental Engineering department of the University of Thrace at Xanthi. Highlighting the importance of new and innovative tools for communities, the event took place on 19-20 October 2022 with a total of 6 lectures explaining the physics behind the services and gathering 43 new total users for A1, A2 and A3.

3.2.2.1 Workshops

The NEANIAS Atmospheric services were presented in the following workshops.

NEANIAS Open Innovation Workshop, Mercure Budapest Korona Hotel, Budapest, Hungary

- Date: May 12th, 2022
- Duration: 2 hours
- Presenters: WP leaders, service providers

NEANIAS Atmospheric Workshop, Elisso Hotel, Xanthi Greece

- Date: June 3rd, 2022
- Duration: 3 hours
- Presenters: Eleni Petra (NKUA), Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Sofia Bressan (UNIMIB), Noela Pina (UBIWHERE)

NEANIAS Atmospheric Workshop, Dept of Physics, NKUA, Athens Greece

- Date: June 28th, 2022
- Duration: 2 hours
- Presenters: Eleni Petra (NKUA), Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Sofia Bressan (UNIMIB), Noela Pina (UBIWHERE)

NEANIAS Atmospheric Workshop, Corallia, Athens Greece

- Date: June 29th, 2022
- Duration: 2 hours
- Presenters: Eleni Petra (NKUA), Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Sofia Bressan (UNIMIB), Noela Pina (UBIWHERE)

2022-06-29: NEANIAS Atmospheric Workshop, Certh, Athens Greece

- Date: June 29th, 2022
- Duration: 2 hours
- Presenters: Eleni Petra (NKUA), Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Sofia Bressan (UNIMIB), Noela Pina (UBIWHERE)

NEANIAS Open Innovation Workshop, ATHENA RC, NKUA, Athens Greece

- Date: September 5th, 2022
- Duration: 5 hours
- Presenters: Eleni Petra (NKUA), Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Sofia Bressan (UNIMIB), Noela Pina (UBIWHERE)

2022-10-26: NEANIAS Open Innovation Workshop, Dept of Physics, NKUA, Athens Greece

- Date: October 26th, 2022
- Duration: 5 hours
- Presenters: Eleni Petra (NKUA), Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Sofia Bressan (UNIMIB), Noela Pina (UBIWHERE)

3.2.2.2 Production of training resources

WP3 service providers have produced documentation for all services locate online [here](#). This includes explaining the scientific approach and user guides.

Additionally, a webinar recording is made available via YouTube here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9kBsTIO6VXY>. In the webinar, all atmospheric services are presented.

The ATMO4CAST service team have added further information on the service documentation to facilitate the user's usage. Furthermore, training material were also prepared, for instance the examples on how to use this service is also provided in the service and was used in different events to facilitate user's engagement and to support NEANIAS Business cases.

3.2.2.3 Practical Lessons

The Atmo-flud service was presented in the Environmental Engineering department of the University of Thrace at Xanthi, during the fall semester of 2021-2022 (October 2021). The service was presented at 6 lectures, and all students were given exercises that utilized this service.

Additionally, the atmospheric services were presented and validated at the Environmental Engineering department of the University of Thrace at Xanthi. Highlighting the importance of new and innovative tools for communities, the event took place on 19-20 October 2022 with a total of 6 lectures explaining the physics behind the services and gathering 43 new total users for A1, A2 and A3.

Practical lessons have been given to **undergraduate students from the University of Milan Bicocca**, showing how to construct the stress field trajectories from local measurements of tectonic and volcano tectonic features by using the NEANIAS WP3-A2 service ATMO-stress. Students used the service and reconstructed the stress field of some selected show cases.

- Date: March, 2021
- Presenter: A. Tibaldi (UNIMIB)

Also, two different workshops were organized by Ubiwhere for students of the University of Aveiro to showcase the NEANIAS WP3-A3 service (Atmo-4CAST):

- Event: Raise your voice towards sustainability (15 May, 2022); Attendance: around 30 participants (students and professors from the Master in Communication and Web Technologies, University of Aveiro). Website information: <https://sites.google.com/ubiwhere.com/mctwubiwhere/home>
- Event: ATMO-4All – Presenting the new cloud-based air quality estimation service. Attendance: around 25 participants (students and researchers with Environmental/Atmospheric science knowledge) Publication: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/712-neanias-presented-at-university-of-aveiro>

3.2.2.4 Geodatathon

The University of Milan Bicocca has organized two different **geodatathon** aimed at undergraduate students, PhD students, researchers and experts in structural geology, geodynamics and seismotectonics. The objective of the events was to show how to use the NEANIAS WP3-A2 ATMO-stress service to reconstruct stress field trajectories from demo and private data. The presenter asked participants to test the service and leave feedback.

- Title “Geodatathon: Ricostruzione delle traiettorie di paleostress attraverso l’ utilizzo del software ATMO-stress”
 - Date: March 28th, 2022
 - Presenter: Sofia Bressan (UNIMIB)
- Title “Geodatathon: the atmo-stress service”
 - Date: October 13th, 2022
 - Presenter: Sofia Bressan (UNIMIB)

3.2.2.5 Participation in conferences and workshops

During the NEANIAS project, the WP3-A2 services will be promoted outside by means of oral and poster presentations at national and international scientific and technical conferences and workshops related to the Earth sciences community. Up to now, the ATMO-stress service has been showcased at the **vPico Presentation in the EGU General Assembly 2021**, held online (19-30 April 2021, session TS 5.4) and in the **EGU General Assembly 2022** (online and in presence, 23-27 May 2022) at the session TS 2.2:

- Falsaperla, S., Tibaldi, A., Corti, N., De Beni, E., Bonali, F. L., Langer, H., Neri, M., Cantarero, M., Reitano, D., and Fallati, L.: Multidisciplinary analyses for mapping and evaluating kinematics and stress/strain field at active faults and fissures at NE Rift, Mt Etna (Italy), EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-4279, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-4279>, 2021.
- Corti, N., Bonali, F. L., Tibaldi, A., Fallati, L., and Russo, E.: UAV-Based Structure-from-Motion Photogrammetry used for reconstructing Late Pleistocene-Holocene deformation: an example from Krafla Rift (NE Iceland), EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-3467, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-3467>, 2021.
- Russo, E., Corti, N., Bonali, F. L., Tibaldi, A., Pasquaré Mariotto, F., Fallati, L., and Marchese, F.: Reconstruction of the entire rift architecture of Theistareykir Fissure Swarm (northeast Iceland): integration between extensive UAV and field surveys, EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-5246, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-5246>, 2021.
- Bressan, S., Gounari, O., Ntouskos V., Corti, N., Bonali, F. L., Karantzalos K. and Tibaldi A.: A new free software to reconstruct stress trajectories: the Atmo-stress service, EGU General Assembly 2022, online presentation, 23-27 May 2022 EGU22-7305, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-7305>, 2022

The NEANIAS project has also been showcased at **the 7th International Conference in Geographical Information Systems Theory, Applications and Management – GISTAM 2021** (23-25 April 2021, online streaming) in the framework of the presentation:

- Bonali, F., Fallati, L., Antoniou, V., Drymoni, K., Mariotto, F., Corti, N., Tibaldi, A., Gudmundsson, A. & Nomikou, P. (2021). Virtual Outcrops Building in Extreme Logistic Conditions for Data Collection, Geological Mapping, and Teaching: The Santorini's Caldera Case Study, Greece. In Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Geographical Information Systems Theory, Applications and Management - GISTAM, ISBN 978-989-758-503-6 ISSN 2184-500X, pages 67-74. DOI: 10.5220/0010419300670074.

The NEANIAS Project and its Atmospheric Services (namely A3 and ADAM platform) have been presented and promoted at **Milano Digital Week 2021**, organised between March 17th and 21st. The session entitled “*DAI SERVIZI CLOUD PER LA SCIENZA APERTA ALLA SOSTENIBILITÀ*”, organised by professor Giuseppe Vizzari where the value proposition of the thematic services was explained to a vast community of students and citizens from Milan, who were invited to experiment the services, provide feedback and participate in the project's open call.

The ATMO-stress service has been also showcased in:

- the **Nordic Geological Winter Meeting**, 11-13 May 2022 on University of Iceland in Reykjavik with a poster presentation:

- Corti, N., Gounari, O., Ntouskos, V., Bressan, S., Bonali F. L., Karantzalos K. and Tibaldi A.: The Atmo-Stress service: a new free web-designed software to reconstruct stress trajectories. The 35th Nordic Geological Winter Meeting 2022, Programme and abstract page 172, number 43. <https://jfi.is/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/NGWM-2022.pdf>

- the **SGI-SIMP congress named “Geosciences for a sustainable future”**, 19-21 September 2022 in Torino, Italy with a poster presentation:

- Bressan, S., Gounari, O., Ntouskos, V., Corti, N., Bonali, F.L., Karantzalos, K. and Tibaldi A.: Atmo-stress cloud service: an open-source tool to reconstruct stress trajectories, SGI-SIMP congress 19-21 Sept 2022 https://geoscienze.org/torino2022/BECong/view_abstract_auth.php?id=6259

Furthermore, the WP3-A3 service (Atmo-4CAST) has also been promoted in different events:

- Vitorino, R. (2021). Suiting the Future of Sustainable Cities. International Conference on Smart, Sustainable, Social and Accessible Tourism, 26 Nov 2021. https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ZgOkL_FEIBWvDSXffWRs9_cpJyA-m-sN/view
- Pina, N., Verdasca, J., Coimbra, L., Vitorino, R. (2022). A new cloud-based service for urban air quality forecast. In Proceedings of 13th International Conference on Air Quality – Science and Application, ISBN: 978-1-3999-2835-9, page 100. DOI: 10.18745/PB.25560. Presentation: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1OxoQDp77tHIP9cOzf4XBoGHvcsg_7qvf/view?usp=sharing

- Barateiro, B. (2022). Investigação para cidades inteligentes e sustentáveis. Roteiro da Sustentabilidade: Inteligência e Inovação no Ambiente Urbano, 28 Apr 2022. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1dKYf1psoALDqYohB5YFC8R4JTr1gsYX4/view>

Finally, NEANIAS Project and the WP3-A3 service (ATMO-4CAST) were also disseminated in the Ubiwhere's exhibitor during Hannover Messe Congress 2022 (30 May to 02 Jun 2022). Hannover Messe is one of the largest trade fairs in the world, dedicated to the topic of industry development, were typically, there are around 6,500 exhibitors and 250,000 visitors.

3.2.2.6 Atmospheric Services User Feedback

During the onboarding activities as well as consequent usage of the Atmospheric services, following the processes defined in the Service Management System that governs the development, delivery, and operation of the NEANIAS services, the end users were invited to provide their feedback on various aspects of the services as perceived by their engagement with them. These responses were collected and aggregated to convey the qualitative and quantitative performance and perceived by the service consumers utilizing user feedback from system usage.

Out of the total number of Atmospheric Service users, a total of 218 users opted to provide feedback on the service usage. The level of domain expertise of these users is showing in the following Figure 10 - Atmospheric domain user expertise.

Figure 10 - Atmospheric domain user expertise

The users were asked to provide their feedback in the following service aspects:

- User Interface Experience
- Evaluation of end results
- Evaluation of service performance
- Willingness to recommend the service

The users were asked to grade their impressions on a scale of 1 to 3, indicating their satisfaction. From Poor to Satisfactory or Excellent.

With respect to the User Interface experience, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 11 - Atmospheric UI/UX across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 12 - Atmospheric UI/UX by user domain expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

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Figure 11 - Atmospheric UI/UX across all users

Figure 12 - Atmospheric UI/UX by user domain expertise

As the figures indicate, the feedback received for the perceived User Experience of the Atmospheric services, the satisfaction is comparably equivalent across the different level of expertise and equally high. This is an indication that the user interface is intuitive and easy to use across expectations coming from users of various relevance to the domain.

The feedback is similarly encouraging when looking into the service result evaluation, as the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 13 - Atmospheric Results across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 14 - Atmospheric Results by domain user expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

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Figure 13 - Atmospheric Results across all users

Figure 14 - Atmospheric Results by domain user expertise

Across the different expertise levels, the results maintain a total of over 90% positive impressions with the excellent impressions ranging from 55% to 70%.

Service performance wise, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 15 - Atmospheric Performance across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 16 - Atmospheric Performance by domain user expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

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Figure 15 - Atmospheric Performance across all users

Figure 16 - Atmospheric Performance by domain user expertise

The pattern observed on the other aspects of the evaluation of the Atmospheric services remains also in the Performance evaluation feedback. Overall, two out of three users of the service find the performance to be excellent while the remaining one of three is at the satisfactory level. Only 1-2% across the low and high domain expertise users find the result poor and this number is 0 for the expert users.

Coming to the important factor of whether the users would be willing to recommend the service to their colleagues, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 17 - Atmospheric

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willingness to recommend across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 18 - Atmospheric willingness to recommend by user domain expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

Figure 17 - Atmospheric willingness to recommend across all users

Figure 18 - Atmospheric willingness to recommend by user domain expertise

Here, while on the overall, cross domain impressions, 9 out of 10 users would be willing to recommend the system, when looking into the broken-down statistics, it seems that for the expert users the percentage is significantly lower. And this is something that the service providers would handle with follow-up processes with their users to improve aspects of their services that could make these users to spread the usage of the services.

3.2.3 Space specific activities

NEANIAS space service providers took active part in the effective dissemination of the project, increasing the penetration of the services within the European astrophysics and planetary science communities through a series of coordinated actions.

3.2.3.1 Production of training resources

Space service providers **produced abundant training resources and support material** that is available online for external users. These include:

- Demo videos on the NEANIAS YouTube channel to present the main goal and characteristics of the services.
- Dedicated webinars for each space service, with a live demonstration showcasing its main functionalities by means of a real-world use case.
- Dedicated thematic portals to easily reach the services and the related information, user manual, documentation and publication:
 - <https://thematic.neanias.eu/SPACE/>
 - <https://neanias-space.openaire.eu/>
- Creation of User Cookbooks complementing the most technical documentation (available at <https://docs.neanias.eu/>), in order to facilitate the users' initial contact with the space services, by providing a simplified, step-by-step user guide.

3.2.3.2 Space Services Webinars

A series of webinars have been organized from April 2022 to June 2022 to present the details of each of the Space Services including a scientific explanation of the potentials of the services and a technical description of the tools and technologies employed for the development and deployment in EOSC.

- Webinar title: "NEANIAS SPACE AstraDataNavigator: Explore our galaxy in virtual reality"
 - Date: April 27th 2022, 10:00 CEST
 - Presenter: Eugenio Topa, Simone Terzuolo (ALTEC)
 - Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/686-astra-data-navigator-service-webinar>
- Webinar title: "NEANIAS SPACE Latent Space Explorer: Unsupervised Data Pattern Discovery on the Cloud"
 - Date: June 7th 2022, 14:30 CEST
 - Presenter: Giuseppe Vizzari, Thomas Ceconello (UNIMIB)
 - Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/728-webinar-on-neanias-lse-service>
- Webinar title: "NEANIAS SPACE ViaLactea: Exploring our galaxy with a multi wavelength approach and visual analytic"
 - Date: June 8th 2022, 15:00 CEST
 - Presenter: Giuseppe Tudisco, Marco Molinaro (INAF), Evgenia Malikova (UoP)

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- Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/730-neanias-space-vialactea-webinar>
- Webinar title: “NEANIAS SPACE CAESAR & AstroML: astronomical source extraction, characterization and classification in the SKA era”
 - Date: June 15th 2022, 15:00 CEST
 - Presenter: Cristobal Bordiu, Simone Riggi (INAF)
 - Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/732-neanias-space-caesar-astroml-webinar>
- Webinar title: “NEANIAS SPACE ADAM-Explorer: Accessing science-ready Mars surface images”
 - Date: June 27th 2022, 15:00 CEST
 - Presenter: Carlos Brandt (JACOBS), Simone Mantovani (MEEO)
 - Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/740-neanias-organized-a-webinar-on-adam-space>

Further information on the SPACE Webinar series can be found at: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/674-neanias-space-webinar-series>

3.2.3.3 Participation in conferences and workshops

During the project lifecycle, NEANIAS space services **will be promoted for onboarding by means of oral and poster contributions in renowned scientific and technical conferences** and workshops related to the astrophysics and planetary science community. As of M18, the events in which NEANIAS service offerings have been showcased are:

- Computing Conference 2020
 - Dates: Jul 16th -17th , 2020
 - Web: <https://saiconference.com/Computing>
 - Contribution: "Towards porting Astrophysics Visual Analytics Services to the European Open Science Cloud" (E. Sciacca)
- European Astronomy Society Annual Meeting 2020
 - Dates: Jun 29th -Jul 3rd , 2020
 - Web: <https://eas.unige.ch/EAS2020/>
 - Contributions: “NEANIAS-Tackling the challenges of future astronomy” (C. Bordiu)
- Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems XXX
 - Dates: Nov 8th -12th , 2020.
 - Web: <https://adass2020.es/>
 - Contributions: “Novel EOSC Services for Space challenges: the NEANIAS first outcomes” (E. Sciacca), “Astronomical research in the next decade: trends, barriers and needs in data access, management, visualization and analysis” (C. Bordiu)
- GARR Workshop 2020
 - Dates: Nov 2th-6th
 - Web: <https://www.eventi.garr.it/it/ws20>

- Contribution: “INAF Sfide e Opportunità di Servizi per l’Astrofisica sulla Cloud GARR: NEANIAS e l’Integrazione in EOSC” (E. Sciacca)
- SPIE Astronomical telescopes and instrumentation
 - Dates: Dec 14th -18th, 2020
 - Web: <https://spie.org/conferences-and-exhibitions/astronomical-telescopes-and-instrumentation>
 - Contributions: “Astrophysics Visual Analytics services on the European Open Science Cloud” (E. Sciacca).
- SKA science conference 2021
 - Dates: March 15th-19th, 2021
 - Web: <https://www.skatelescope.org/skascicon21/>
 - Contributions: “Searching and characterizing extended sources in the MeerKAT Galactic Plane Survey” (S. Riggi), “Astrophysics Visual Analytics Services on the Cloud for Open Science Toward SKA” (E. Sciacca), "Radio-astronomical image segmentation with Tiramisu and Mask R-CNN" (R. Sortino).
- Milano Digital Week 2021
 - Dates: March 17th-21st, 2021
 - Web: <https://www.milanodigitalweek.com/>
 - Contributions: "Portiamos gli astri sulla Cloud" (G. Vizzari)
- Applications of Statistical Methods and ML in the Space Sciences
 - Dates: May 17th-21st, 2021
 - Web: <http://spacescience.org/workshops/mlconference2021.php>
 - Contributions: "Towards a modern unsupervised ML approach to the analysis of astrophysics images" (T. Cecconello, C. Bordiu).
- 2021 Planetary Data Workshop
 - Web: <https://www.hou.usra.edu/meetings/planetdata2021/>
 - Dates: June 28–July 2, 2021 - Virtual
 - Birds-of-a-Feather: Geologic Mapping (JACOBS + MEEO) <https://forum.openplanetary.org/t/birds-of-a-feather-geologic-mapping/501/3>
- Europlanet Science Congress 2021 (EPSC2021)
 - Dates: 13 – 24 September 2021 (Virtual)
 - Web:
 - Talk: "Planetary Geologic Mapping with Europlanet GMAP" (A. Rossi, JACOBS)
- ESA Φ-week 2021
 - Dates: 11 to 15 October 2021 (Virtual)
 - Web:
 - e-Poster: "EOSC Space Services For the Planetary Data Research" (MEEO)
- The Third National Workshop on the SKA Project - The Italian Route to the SKAO Revolution
 - Dates: 4-8 October 2021 (Virtual)

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- Web:
- Talk: "Visualization and source analysis services for the SKA Regional Centers" (Simone Riggi, INAF)
- VII International Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Pattern Recognition
 - Dates: 5 - 7 October 2021 (Virtual)
 - Web: N/A
 - Talk: "Semantic Segmentation of Radio-astronomical Images" (Carmelo Pino, INAF)
- ADASS 2021 Astronomy. Software. Systems. ADASS XXXI
 - Web: <https://www.adass2021.ac.za/>
 - Dates: 24 – 28 October 2021
 - Poster: "Onboarding SPACE services to the European Open Science Cloud" (Presenter: E. Sciacca)
 - Poster: "ViaLactea: a distributed Visual Analytic system for exploring our Galactic ecosystem" (Presenter: G. Tudiaco)
 - Poster: "Latent Space Explorer: Unsupervised Data Pattern Discovery on the Cloud" (Presenter: T. Ceconello)
 - Poster: "Radio source analysis services for the SKA and precursors" (Presenter: S. Riggi)
- 20th International Conference of the Italian Association for Artificial Intelligence (AIxIA2021)
 - Web: <https://underline.io/lecture/42158-unsupervised-data-pattern-discovery-on-the-cloud> (video of the presentation)
 - <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3078/paper-52.pdf> (paper)
 - Date: 3 December 2021
 - Paper: "Unsupervised Data Pattern Discovery on the Cloud" (Presenter: G. Vizzari)
- GeoPython 2022
 - Web: <https://2022.geopython.net/>
 - Date: 20 – 22 June 2022
 - Talk: "Cloud for Mars: python tools to planetary data access through EOSC" (Carlos H. Brandt, JacobsUni)
- EAS 2022 International Conference
 - Web: <https://eas.unige.ch/EAS2022/>
 - Dates: 27 June – 1 July 2022, Valencia, Spain
 - Talk: "An unsupervised take on the Galactic Supernova Remnant population" Presenters: (F. Bufano, C. Bordiu) see <https://eas2022programme.kuoni-congress.info/presentation/an-unsupervised-take-on-the-galactic-supernova-remnant-population>
 - e-Poster: "A benchmark on Deep Learning methods for Radio Astronomical images Object Detection and Segmentation" see <https://eas2022programme.kuoni-congress.info/presentation/a-benchmark-on-deep-learning-methods-for-radio-astronomical->

[images-object-detection-and-segmentation](#)

3.2.3.4 Organization of Conferences and Workshops/Hackathons

Different events were organized in the course of the project to promote the exploitation of NEANIAS space services within the community.

- ML4ASTRO International Conference on Machine Learning for Astrophysics.
 - Web: <https://indico.ict.inaf.it/event/1692/>
 - Date: 30 May 2022 - 1 June 2022
 - Venue: Catania, Italy
 - 200 Participants
 - This event brought together astrophysicists and Machine Learning experts from all around the world to showcase their work, discuss common problems and explore synergies in the application of cutting-edge Machine Learning techniques to astrophysical problems.
- Hack The Science 2022
 - Web: <https://sites.google.com/unimib.it/hack-the-science-2022/>
 - Date: 25 Jun 2022 – 28 July 2022
 - Venue: online
 - 30 participants
 - A hackathon about data science, cloud computing and user experience, presenting three challenges (Hack the Planets, Hack the Stellar Populations and Hack the UX of NEANIAS) to be tackled by multidisciplinary teams of up to 3 participants, who were asked to find innovative solutions by extensively using the NEANIAS Space Services.

3.2.3.5 Collaboration with other European Projects

Exploitation of synergies with other European projects, such as ESCAPE - European Science Cluster for Astronomy and Particle Physics⁶ and ERC ECOGAL⁷, looking for **potential collaborations and joint initiatives** that benefit from common or shared thematic and target communities, with the goal of promoting the NEANIAS space services offerings reaching as many users as possible.

Furthermore, NEANIAS, in collaboration with the CIRASA project, is playing a key role in the materialization of the SKA Regional Centers, aimed at providing end users (the radio community) with data access and processing resources in a transparent way. In order to meet

⁶ <https://projectescape.eu/>

⁷ <http://www.ecogal.eu/>

the performance and scalability demands of SKA and its precursors, ViaLactea and CAESAR represent the cornerstone to build an ecosystem of cloud services for efficient archive data retrieval, visualization and source analysis integrated into a common visual analytic platform. Finally, The GMAP⁸ (Geologic MAPPING of Planetary bodies) project, part of the Europlanet 2024 Research Infrastructure, makes use of NEANIAS planetary services to provide Mars basemaps and data exploration through ADAM Space-Explorer, and the backend services Docker-ISIS, ADAM-API, Mosaic and data reduction Python tools.

3.2.3.6 Space Services User Feedback

During the onboarding activities as well as consequent usage of the Space services, following the processes defined in the Service Management System that governs the development, delivery, and operation of the NEANIAS services, the end users were invited to provide their feedback on various aspects of the services as perceived by their engagement with them. These responses were collected and aggregated to convey the qualitative and quantitative performance and perceived by the service consumers utilizing user feedback from system usage.

Out of the total number of Space Service users, a total of 164 users opted to provide feedback on the service usage. The level of domain expertise of these users is showing in the following Figure 19 - Space domain user expertise.

Figure 19 - Space domain user expertise

For the Space services, there was a 23% of the users providing feedback, for which their domain affiliation was not determined and are not included in the statistics that present the feedback based on the user domain expertise.

The users were asked to provide their feedback in the following service aspects:

- User Interface Experience

⁸ <https://www.europlanet-gmap.eu>

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- Evaluation of end results
- Evaluation of service performance
- Willingness to recommend the service

The users were asked to grade their impressions on a scale of 1 to 3, indicating their satisfaction. From Poor to Satisfactory or Excellent.

With respect to the User Interface experience, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 20 - Space UI/UX across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 21 - Space UI/UX by user domain expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

Figure 20 - Space UI/UX across all users

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Figure 21 - Space UI/UX by user domain expertise

As the figures indicate, the feedback received for the perceived User Experience of the Space services, the satisfaction is predominantly positive, judged as excellent by more the 50% of the users, regardless of their experience level.

A similar view can be observed in the feedback received for the service result evaluation, as the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 22 - Space Results across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 23 - Space Results by domain user expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

Figure 22 - Space Results across all users

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Figure 23 - Space Results by domain user expertise

Across the different expertise levels, for the feedback where the information is available, the results maintain a total of 100% positive impressions with the excellent impressions ranging from 60% to 75%.

Service performance wise, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 24 - Space Performance across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 25 - Space Performance by domain user expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

Figure 24 - Space Performance across all users

Figure 25 - Space Performance by domain user expertise

For the performance evaluation of the Space services, the overall feedback remains positive to a significant percentage, ranging from 75% to 85% of the users providing feedback. Across the different domain expertise levels though, one can observe that for the high domain expertise level users, the “excellent” level responses are more than double than for the expert ones, while for the low expertise, it reaches approximately 10% of the responses. While the overall feedback remains positive, this may indicate different expectations from the different user classifications that may be worth additional investigation from the service providers.

Coming to the important factor of whether the users would be willing to recommend the service to their colleagues, the following figures highlight the findings. Figure 26 - Space willingness to recommend across all users presents the user feedback regardless of their domain expertise, while Figure 27 - Space willingness to recommend by user domain expertise presents the findings in relation to the user domain expertise.

Figure 26 - Space willingness to recommend across all users

Figure 27 - Space willingness to recommend by user domain expertise

Also in this measured feedback, the overall positive remarks can be observed. Approximately 90% of the users would be willing to recommend the services across the different experience levels.

3.3 Core Services Onboarding

Core services are directly integrated into other core and thematic services. Consequently, the experiences of onboarding for Thematic services will be leveraged upon appropriately to develop them further, in order to build specific Core services onboarding activities. Such activities will be designed and carried out by WP6 partners in close collaboration with the Thematic Work Packages, with the aim of promoting jointly both the Core and Thematic service offerings of NEANIAS. Furthermore, the partners of WP6 will take every opportunity

to advertise and promote the core services on various upcoming workshops, conferences and events to raise awareness and interest. Direct communication (advertisements) towards potential scientific groups and communities (which are closely related to the WP6 partners) will also be initiated.

In this respect, *Artificial Intelligence (C3)* and *Visualization (C4)* core services have a particular attractiveness for external users. Owing to their general-purpose, traversal nature, these services can be easily adapted or extended beyond their original scope (e.g. to visualize or analyse other types of scientific data, not necessarily related to Underwater, Atmospheric or Space sectors). This enormously facilitates the design of specific onboarding strategies, highlighting the potential of these and their successful application to the NEANIAS science use cases. These strategies may involve a number of complementary actions, including but not limited to:

- **targeted advertisement toward specific groups** of potential users interested in novel developments on Visualization, Data Analysis and Machine Learning (both from academic and industry sectors).
- Participation and promotion of the services in **generalist Computer Vision, AI and ML conferences and workshops**.

In particular, the following activities helped to promote the NEANIAS core services among potential target communities:

- Webinar entitled: “*NEANIAS Visualization Gateway: an EOSC Gateway for scientific visualization*”
 - Date: June 22nd 2022, 15:00 CEST
 - Presenter: Benjamin Kyd (UoP)
 - Link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/activities/737-webinar-on-visualization-gateway-neanias-core-service>
- Video on the AI-Gateway and Horovod service
 - Web: <https://youtu.be/eJbxHm-nXc>
- Participation in the Conference “From Science Gateways to Papers”
 - Date: 23–26 May 2022
 - Location: Palermo, Italy
 - Talk: “*The advantages of Notebooks orbiting the Cloud*” (INAF)
- Participation in the 14th International Workshop on Science Gateways
 - Date: 15th-17th June 2022
 - Location: Trento, Italy
 - Talk: “*Science Gateways in EOSC: The NEANIAS Visualisation Gateway*” (Eva Sciacca, Mario Raciti, INAF, and Mel Krokos and Benjamin Kyd, UoP)
- Participation in the EGI conference 2022
 - Web: <https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2022/>
 - Date: 19 – 23 September 2022
 - Talk: “*Distributed Deep Learning by Horovod - a new EOSC service*” (Jozsef Kovacs, SZTAKI)
- Participation in the Neanias Open Event 2022

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- Web: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/events/neanias-open-event>
- Date: 22 – 23 September 2022
- Talk: "*Distributed Deep Learning by Horovod*" (Attila Farkas, Krisztian Pora, SZTAKI)

Finally, two scientific publications describing the aims, technical details (implementation, architecture) and future prospects of the NEANIAS core services have been published, namely:

- Sciacca, Eva, et al. "*Scientific Visualization on the Cloud: the NEANIAS Services towards EOSC Integration.*" *Journal of Grid Computing* 20.1 (2022): 1-18.
- Attila Farkas, Krisztián Póra, Sándor Szénási, Gábor Kertész, Róbert Lovas, "*Evaluation of a distributed deep learning framework as a reference architecture for a cloud environment*", 10th Jubilee IEEE International Conference on Computational Cybernetics and Cyber-Medical Systems (ICCC), 2022 (in press).

3.4 Business opportunities and innovation (Open Call)

European Start-ups often face difficulties in the early phases, mostly because of the lack of high-quality infrastructure and human resources available to test and efficiently develop their technology. NEANIAS aims to provide technical and financial support to tackle these challenges. To **boost the development of new business opportunities and accelerate the onboarding of external users** into the project, NEANIAS organized two Open Calls, for Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Science initiatives. The **purpose of the Open Calls was to spark and support the development of a wide variety of innovation projects**, by providing novel services created in the frame of the NEANIAS project, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations and contributing to advance research and innovation in Europe. The overarching goal was to build up and strengthen the European innovation community by identifying and supporting innovative projects with novel services developed in the Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research fields. Innovation in this scope may refer to (a) new operation models for existing services, that can exploit NEANIAS resources (b) improving existing services utilizing NEANIAS offerings to increase their overall offering (c) brand new services inspired by NEANIAS offerings (d) new services in need offerings such as NEANIAS and EOSC ones, and many more. The Open Call applicants had to demonstrate in the frame of an interview with NEANIAS experts, that as a result of collaborating with NEANIAS experts, they can create novel technologies with long-term added value and sustainability.

The 1st Open Call was launched on the 8 February 2021 and was closed on the 9 April 2021. The 2nd Open Call was launched in on the 11 October 2021, with the application deadline of 8 December, 2021. The challenge was to find innovative projects with technological and business potential, that could utilize the NEANIAS services, develop novel technologies and strengthen European researches in the Atmosphere, Underwater and Space service sectors. (www.neanias.eu)

NEANIAS Partners conducted a centralised effort in terms of communication (details stated in D5.4) and to provide all information about the opportunity in applying for the Open Call.

Target groups, reached out by NEANIAS experts:

- Start-ups

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- Established private companies from diverse industries (SMEs / Multinationals)
- Groups of individual researchers / innovators of up to 3 members

The added values of NEANIAS were communicated by each Thematic sector representatives to their target audience.

As a result of the intense communication campaign, and individual discussions with potential applicants, altogether 7 external business cases were selected from altogether 26 applicants in the frame of the Open Calls.

The selection of applications was concluded with the participation of the Open Call Evaluation Board representing each thematic field. In the next round, **the applicants are invited for an interview with the assigned NEANIAS experts** to provide further information about their project and discuss about the possible collaboration opportunities.

The final selection of the winners took place in the frame of a discussion with the participation of the Open Call Evaluation Board, then the onboarding process started between the selected applicants and the NEANIAS experts.

The provided services by NEANIAS for the winners of the Open Call:

- Access to NEANIAS Thematic Services
- Support on business development
- Networking
- Promotion

The list of the selected projects:

<u>1st Open Call Winners</u>	
Geoinsight	Hungary
OWL	Portugal
ENALIATEC	Greece

<u>2nd Open Call Winners</u>	
DDQ	The Netherlands
Relief Applications	Spain
Walldone	Greece
Sotiria	Greece

Brief description of the business cases:

1st Open Call:

Geoinsight focuses on Mobile cell data aggregation tool to monetise human mobility data, meeting privacy and data protection requirements

OWL intends to quantify air pollution and understand its temporal evolution in the urban context, using the Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting service.

ENALIATEC deals with 3D Seabed Mapping and Classification Utilizing Sonar-Based Information: The goal of EnaliaTec within this Open Call is twofold: (a) to develop an algorithm for 3D seabed geolocated mapping utilizing sonar information, and (b) to develop a system for categorizing/ recognizing objects at the 3D seabed.

2nd Open Call:

DDQ created an EOSC-capable back-end service/platform for mobile (smartphone+sensor) based observations. This offers one back-end service for multiple applications (for example Biodiversity and Environmental). They are looking to enrich the back end with AI and forecasting models and implement GEO standards.

Relief aims to create the first affordable professional search system with dogs and drones, able to offer search teams information in real time about dog paths, atmospheric information and drone images and thermal data.

Walldone aim is to create a web-based, flexible and adaptable "mechanism" to manage more effectively the transformation of the built environment towards climate neutrality, in the context of smart cities.

SOTIRIA Technology current expertise is based on 3 pillars: AI, magnetic sensors and passive hydrophones. They would like to design high quality renders to showcase the deployment of their technology with the integration of NEANIAS services.

After completing the selection of the open call applications, the selected business cases went through an individual onboarding process, which covered technical and business onboarding. The technical onboarding process dealt with the integration of NEANIAS services and finding the way they can be integrated with a high added value (details are in D5.2 and D5.3). The business onboarding process included a business coaching of the business cases, with the aim to find the most appropriate fields of utilising the technologies and create sustainable added values on a long run. The aim of the onboarding process was to create a technology and business model, which will be sustainable after the completion of NEANIAS. As part of the business and technical onboarding of the business cases Open Innovation workshops were organised in person on the 5 September 2022 and on the 26 October. The aim of the Open Innovation workshops was to collect user feedbacks to identify new development areas for each service, and discuss the further steps of development. To ensure sustainability from a business perspective, further business opportunities were identified, that would ensure the exploitation and sustainability of each thematic service.

4. Conclusions and Future Steps

This deliverable summarizes the overall training and user onboarding activities in NEANIAS. These activities **fostered awareness raising and capacity delivery** on NEANIAS service offerings, highlighting the potential of the developed services for the target research communities, and contributing to the creation of a **solid and growing user base**.

In the course of the project, multiple training and onboarding activities have been successfully implemented, bringing together the relevant actors in the services' lifecycle, i.e. internal users (developers/providers) and external (end) users, allowing for raising interest, providing technical training and acquiring valuable inputs and feedback. However, besides the development and delivery of cutting-edge technological solutions for the underwater, atmospheric and space research communities, **NEANIAS seeks to onboard these communities onto the Open Science paradigm**, introducing researchers to the benefits of collaborative and reproducible science in the EOSC framework. By embracing open science practices, research communities will **unlock new opportunities and discoveries**, only possible through a close collaboration across diverse areas. NEANIAS thus **strengthened research communities** both directly, by means of its service offerings, and indirectly, through the nurturing of the concepts that support the interdisciplinary research era.

The long-term sustainability of NEANIAS service offerings depends also on the **developed reliable onboarding strategies** that contributed to enlarge and support the NEANIAS (and EOSC) user base, also facilitating the **communication between target communities and service providers**. Indeed, feedback from end-users was critical for the Technical and Strategy boards in order to fine tune the services' capabilities to the ever-increasing, ever-evolving needs of the research communities. The successful materialization of a collaborative research ecosystem required a **compromise between service providers, stakeholders and policy-makers** to produce a suitable framework that encourages and supports researchers in the adoption of Open Science practices and FAIR principles. In this context, aspects such as a close contact with universities and research institutions, the recurrent organization and participation of NEANIAS in events such as the Blue Research and Innovation Week, or the exploitation of synergies with other European projects and initiatives bound to the Open Science paradigm, are of the utmost importance to bridge the current gap between the research community and the Open Science paradigm.

References

- [1] NEANIAS WP7 Collaboration, “D7.6 - Training & user onboarding activities report (interim)”, NEANIAS, 2021 ([link](#))
- [2] NEANIAS WP2 Collaboration, “D2.9 - Underwater Thematic Services Assessment Report”, NEANIAS, 2022 ([link](#))
- [3] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, “D3.9 - Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report”, NEANIAS, 2022 ([link](#))
- [4] NEANIAS WP4, “D4.9 - Space Thematic Services Assessment Report”, NEANIAS, 2022 ([link](#))

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication & Authorisation Infrastructure
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
ML	Machine Learning
REST	Representational State Transfer
RDM	Research Data Management
SKA	Square Kilometre Array
SME	Small & Medium Enterprises
TRL	Technology Readiness Level